

A Review on the Artificial Intelligence in Academia

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Abstract

ChatGPT's emergence in 2022 marked a turning point for AI adoption, catalyzing an era of boom that revolutionized many spheres, especially academia. This review focuses on the impact of AI on academic circles with a view toward ethical implications: scientific fraud and challenges raised by AI-generated content that is getting closer to human writing. AI "hallucinations"-misleading outputs-fuel concerns about misinformation. Using AI tools in academic research and education brings ethical and legal issues. This paper aims to review the relevant literature to identify research gaps; it also puts into perspective the increasing need for enhanced AI text detectors, complemented by equally innovative test redesigns, in the quest to protect scientific integrity. Limitations in AI detection and novel ways to foil academic deceit are areas where further research should be explored. This is amongst areas of ethical guidelines and work on scientific image detectors.

Keywords: AI in Academia, ChatGPT, AI Boom, Ethical Implications, Scientific Fraud, AI-Generated Content, Academic Integrity, AI Hallucinations, Misinformation, AI Detection Tools, Academic Dishonesty, Research Gaps, Test Redesign, Legal Issues in AI.

A Review on the Artificial Intelligence in Academia

Introduction

The introduction of ChatGPT, which was released in December of 2022, has been credited with making Artificial Intelligence (AI) more mainstream and causing an "AI Boom," according to Weise et al. (2023). AI's ease of use and ability to generate text similar to humans have led to further growth and possibilities (U.S. Government Accountability Office, 2023). Academics, in particular, have been impacted by the "AI Boom" in various fields (Livberber & Ayvaz, 2023). Nevertheless, concerns remain, particularly within academia, about the misuse of AI, as seen with Generative AI (Currie & Quach, 2023). These concerns are made harder to detect due to artificial intelligence becoming better over time and how the generated content looks similar to human text (Dergaa et al., 2023).

One threat that AI poses is an increase in misinformation tied to AI 'hallucination' (Monteith et al., 2023). Hallucination with artificial intelligence is defined in recent research and the Merriam-Webster dictionary as misleading or incorrect outputs (Maleki et al., 2024; "Hallucination," 2024). More significant issues are with the ethicality and legality of using models like ChatGPT, despite being usable in fields such as Medical Research and as a teaching tool (Khlaif et al., 2023). As a result of this potential fraud, the implications and to investigate them further, we have posed the question: "How do artificial intelligence and AI tools impact academic integrity and the originality of academic papers?" We have decided to answer this question from another perspective: reviewing existing research on the topic and coming up with further gaps in research after the "AI Boom."

Methodology

Search terms such as “AI Academic Integrity” among other relevant features building on research gaps already demonstrated were utilized in databases such as Google Scholar and JSTOR to locate and identify papers and relevant resources. They would be initially included or excluded based on their relevance to the research question and the overall topic. The final included research papers are then analyzed to identify a gap that could further be built on in future papers among practices to be utilized.

Review

The primary focus related to academic integrity and Artificial Intelligence concerns has been preventing academic dishonesty by redesigning assessments. According to Sullivan et al., universities could redesign assessments in a way that couldn't be completed by AI tools with frequent opportunities for cheating demonstrating this (Sullivan et al., 2023). The limitations of Sullivan et al. research were a smaller sample size, which could be improved by more diversity in news outlets as the research used Western sources. A larger sample size of papers and a better understanding of academic dishonesty can help overcome these limitations that have impacted Sullivan et al.'s findings.

Despite the limitations, the effectiveness of preventing academic dishonesty by redesigning assignments is highlighted by teaching strategies from the University of Massachusetts Amherst where examples to prevent/be replicated by AI can be from a presentation with a Q&A to being able to provide proof of doing the assignment themselves through the utilization of version history (*How Do I (Re)Design Assignments and Assessments in an AI-Impacted World? : Center for Teaching & Learning : UMass Amherst*, n.d.). The teaching strategies being demonstrated are essential as they come from a reputable institution and align

with Sullivan et al.'s findings (2023), reinforcing the further need for adjustments in assessment design to prevent academic dishonesty.

While redesigning assessments and implementing teaching strategies are important in being able to combat academic dishonesty with artificial intelligence, another perspective for the usage of artificial intelligence in academia that could be explored is building a text-detector for checking text developed by artificial intelligence, with research opening up to detecting AI-authored content. This can be seen in Anderson et al. (2023), where they conducted an experiment utilizing essays written by ChatGPT, finding out that the difference between produced and original abstracts in research papers was difficult to discern, with the change in paraphrasing leading from a 0.02% human-generated content to 99.52%. Since it is difficult to discern, further innovation into space and the ability to detect AI-generated content may be possible.

As Anderson et al. have observed, it is possible to detect AI-generated content better. This is supported by Weber-Wulff et al.'s research later in 2023. According to them, artificial intelligence-generated content systems are unsustainable for evidence in a case of academic dishonesty, as they often produce false positives and false negatives. In addition, they advise educators to emphasize preventative measures, emphasize the need for multiple teaching methods, and to conduct future research to evaluate the performance of AI-generated text detection tools with various levels of obfuscation, a combination of human and artificially generated text among the impact of student learning, and exploring the legal implications (Weber-Wulff et al., 2023). As a result of these findings, further innovation can take place, and artificial content can be detected more easily. As a result, better tools can be developed to detect

the content. By obfuscating testing performance of detectors and by building a detector tailored specifically for academia, some further gaps in research could be filled.

Another area that had been focused on with the use of artificial intelligence in academia was the generation of fake papers. In 2023, Májovsk et al. evaluated the production of fake medical papers using artificial intelligence (AI) such as ChatGPT, with considerations for expert review and improvements to the paper needed for the paper to be submitted to PLOS Medicine, as well as the fact that the paper had some issues but could be used in scientific fraud. A detector had also been used, which had not been confidently assessed as AI-generated and was able to improve (Májovský et al., 2023). Some journals could develop ethical guidelines to detect artificially generated content based on the possible shortcomings with detectors. In light of this, a more accurate detection strategy must be developed, and one of the possible methods is through the training of models. The issue of scientific fraud is not the only issue raised; also concerns about image fraud within scientific papers, which may deceive researchers & communities.

Gu et al. support this sentiment regarding image fraud. Based on the detection of synthetic images by forensic tools being better for detecting natural images, but not scientific images, it is difficult to detect such image fraud within being noticed by humans. As a result of image fraud, reviewers are deceived, scientific communities are misled, and resources may be wasted, but it also leads to the deception of reviewers, misled scientific communities, and the possible loss of resources. It is important to place emphasis on better detecting scientific images in order to prevent such research fraud and deception in the scientific community. Since it has been the only point of view in recent years, scientific synthetic image detection has another shortcoming within existing research that could be addressed.

Discussion

Based on the results obtained from the review, artificial intelligence is becoming increasingly important in academia, particularly in redefining traditional definitions of academic integrity and originality. According to our findings, accurate detection methods can be used to enhance academic writing as well as better image recognition by using AI. Despite AI's potential as an advanced research tool, it can also result in AI "hallucinations". Consequently, misleading content is likely to be published, causing confusion for readers and individuals, as well as leading to research being published.

Artificial Intelligence is, however, starting to push administrators and institutions to reconsider traditional forms of assessment. To combat academic dishonesty, assessments can be redesigned so that AI cannot complete them autonomously. It is clear, however, that future research should focus on developing and working on more advanced detection tools to distinguish between human-generated and AI-generated text, and even scientific images. As researchers, it is our responsibility to preserve the sanctity and integrity of academic writing within the context of the deception posed and implications seen with scientific image generation. We have, however, been limited by the lack of use of many sources for more nuanced perspectives and a lack of research on specific aspects of identifying sources. There is a clear gap in recent research published on image fraud by artificial intelligence, leading to a perspective that should be explored as a result of the lack of specific perspective.

Researchers should focus on creating robust and accurate AI detection that can detect not only the use of generative AI in text and images, but also "humanizing" tools that can mask the use of AI through paraphrasing and obfuscation. In addition, as AI develops, comprehensive ethical guidelines and legal frameworks will be crucial for regulating its use in academia.

Conclusion

In the years since ChatGPT was released, AI has grown and led to further advancements in Artificial Intelligence and the transformation of industries (Rashid & Kausik, 2024). As a result of these changes, academic integrity has been a subject of concern within academia. We asked ourselves “How do artificial intelligence and AI tools impact academic integrity and originality?” We decided to answer this question through a review of artificial intelligence within academia. As a result, recent research was reviewed. According to our findings, redesigning assessments was considered; however, there has been a lack of knowledge and a need for a better solution to detect artificially generated content, as well as scientific image fraud, utilizing artificial intelligence-generated images. A key implication of our findings is that artificial intelligence can mislead communities, especially scientific communities, through its use, deception, and further dishonesty if there are no standards for better detection and policy practices (Dolunay & Temel, 2024). Within academia, future research should mainly focus on the detection of artificially generated images amongst regular text, as well as investigating why images generated aren't detectable or have low detection rates, and why text has a high possibility of false positives. Recently, however, ethical policies need to be addressed as well.

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